

Synthesis and characterization of some transition metal complexes with 4-(phenyl/*p*-bromophenyl)thiazolyl hydrazone of furfural

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Manuscript received 26 July 2006, revised 1 August 2007, accepted 7 August 2007

Abstract : Complexes of the type $[ML_2X_2]$, where L = 2-(furfurylidine-imino-amino)-4-phenylthiazole (FPT) or 2-(furfurylidine-imino-amino)-4-(*p*-bromophenyl)thiazole (FBPT), M = Co^{II}, Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} and X = Cl⁻, Br⁻ or NO₃⁻ have been synthesized and characterized on the basis of elemental analysis, molar conductance, magnetic moment, thermal analysis together with electronic and IR spectral data. The results are in consistent with bidentate chelation of ligand with azo methine nitrogen and ring sulphur atom as bonding sites as inferred from IR spectra while the complexes of above stoichiometry are found to be in approximately octahedral environment; the symmetry being C₂ for Co^{II} complexes and D_{4h} for others. From the results, the coexistence of paramagnetic and diamagnetic Ni^{II} centers has been established.

Keywords : Thiazolyl hydrazone, furfural, transition metal complexes.

As a part of our continuing research on the studies of metal complexes with bioactive ligands containing NOS donor¹, we report here synthesis and structural studies on the complexes of Co^{II}, Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} with some hydrazone derivatives containing thiazole moiety such as 2-(furfurylidine-imino-amino)-4-phenylthiazole (FPT) and 2-(furfurylidine-imino-amino)-4-(*p*-bromophenyl)thiazole (FBPT) as shown in Fig. 1.

[Y = Phenyl or *p*-bromophenyl moiety]

Fig. 1

Results and discussion

The analytical data exhibit 1 : 2 (M : L) stoichiometry for all the metal complexes and the low molar conductance values in DMSO indicate them to be non electrolytes (Table 1).

The IR spectra of the ligands show multiple band system in the region 3200–3060 cm⁻¹ assignable to N–H and C–H stretching vibration of imino NH, phenyl and thiazolyl groups. The position of this band system re-

mains unaltered in the present complexes indicating non coordination of imino nitrogen atom in complexation. The characteristics IR bands observed at ~1500, ~1300 and ~850 cm⁻¹ are assignable to ν_{C=N} (cyclic), ν_{C-N} (cyclic) and C–S–C mode of vibration of thiazole moiety. The position of the later band shifts to lower frequency region by 10–20 cm⁻¹ in all the complexes, where as the former two bands remain practically unaltered indicating the coordination of ring sulphur atom to the metal ion.

Besides the above, the bands occurring at ~1600 and 1010 cm⁻¹ assignable to the azomethine ν_{C=N} and ν_{N-N} of the ligand shifted their position on complexation. The ν_{C=N} band shows red shift where as ν_{N-N} band shows blue shift there by implying the coordination of azomethine nitrogen atom to the metal ion. Therefore, in the light of the IR spectral data the ligand FPT/FBPT acts as a neutral bidentate ligands; the bonding sites being azomethine nitrogen and ring sulphur atom leading to the bis complex of the type $[ML_2X_2]$. The IR spectral evidence for the bonding of anionic part is as follows, in the nitrate complexes four additional band at ~1380, ~1040, ~810 and ~770 cm⁻¹ are observed. These spectral features provide unequivocal evidence for coordination of nitrate groups in unidentate manner under C_{2v} symmetry². The coordination of azomethine nitrogen atom and nitrate anion through oxygen atom is further confirm by the presence of bands at ~520 and ~460 cm⁻¹ assignable to M–N

Table 1. Analytical and molar conductance data of complexes

Compd.	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)							Δ_m ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)
	M	C	N	H	S	Cl	Br	
[Co(FPT) ₂ Cl ₂]	8.82 (8.85)	50.30 (50.32)	12.57 (12.60)	3.29 (3.31)	9.58 (9.57)	10.62 (10.65)	-	8.2
[Co(FPT) ₂ Br ₂]	7.78 (7.80)	44.38 (44.41)	11.01 (11.11)	2.90 (2.92)	8.45 (8.47)	-	21.13 (21.16)	7.8
[Co(FPT) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]	8.17 (8.19)	46.60 (46.63)	15.53 (15.55)	3.05 (3.08)	8.88 (8.89)	-	-	8.8
[Co(FBPT) ₂ Cl ₂]	7.11 (7.14)	40.58 (40.61)	10.14 (10.17)	2.65 (2.69)	7.73 (7.75)	8.57 (8.60)	19.32 (19.34)	21.2
[Co(FBPT) ₂ Br ₂]	6.42 (6.44)	36.64 (36.67)	9.16 (9.18)	2.39 (2.41)	6.97 (6.99)	-	34.89 (34.92)	21.4
[Co(FBPT) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]	6.61 (6.63)	38.14 (38.16)	12.71 (12.74)	2.49 (2.51)	7.26 (7.28)	-	18.16 (18.18)	20.8
[Ni(FPT) ₂ Cl ₂]	8.79 (8.82)	50.32 (50.34)	12.58 (12.59)	3.29 (3.31)	9.58 (9.60)	10.63 (10.65)	-	12.2
[Ni(FPT) ₂ Br ₂]	7.75 (7.78)	44.40 (44.41)	11.66 (11.69)	2.90 (2.92)	8.45 (8.47)	-	21.14 (21.16)	18.14
[Ni(FPT) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]	8.14 (8.18)	46.62 (46.64)	15.54 (15.55)	3.05 (3.07)	8.88 (8.90)	-	-	20.02
[Ni(FBPT) ₂ Cl ₂]	7.11 (7.08)	40.59 (40.58)	10.15 (10.17)	2.65 (2.67)	7.73 (7.75)	8.57 (8.58)	19.33 (19.35)	20.80
[Ni(FBPT) ₂ Br ₂]	6.40 (6.42)	36.65 (36.67)	9.16 (9.18)	2.39 (2.40)	6.98 (6.99)	-	34.90 (34.91)	20.24
[Ni(FBPT) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]	6.66 (6.68)	38.15 (38.17)	12.72 (12.74)	2.49 (2.52)	7.26 (7.28)	-	18.16 (18.18)	21.42
[Cu(FPT) ₂ Cl ₂]	9.44 (9.45)	49.96 (49.99)	12.49 (12.51)	3.27 (3.30)	9.51 (9.52)	10.55 (10.57)	-	11.2
[Cu(FPT) ₂ Br ₂]	8.33 (8.34)	44.12 (44.14)	11.03 (11.06)	2.88 (2.90)	8.40 (8.44)	-	21.01 (21.03)	20.3
[Cu(FPT) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]	8.75 (8.77)	46.13 (46.33)	15.43 (15.44)	3.03 (3.05)	8.82 (8.84)	-	-	9.2
[Cu(FBPT) ₂ Cl ₂]	7.62 (7.65)	40.36 (40.38)	10.08 (10.11)	2.64 (2.65)	7.68 (7.71)	8.52 (8.54)	19.21 (19.22)	21.48
[Cu(FBPT) ₂ Br ₂]	6.89 (6.91)	36.46 (36.47)	9.11 (9.14)	2.38 (2.40)	6.94 (6.96)	-	34.72 (34.75)	22.24
[Cu(FBPT) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]	7.17 (7.19)	37.94 (37.96)	12.64 (12.68)	2.48 (2.51)	7.22 (7.24)	-	-	22.82

and M-O stretching vibration respectively.

Although evidence of M-S, M-Cl and M-Br bands could not be brought out in present investigation, the insolubility of these complexes in water and their non electrolytic nature provide sufficient evidence for covalence of the counter anion.

An examination of the thermogram of FPT complexes (Fig. 2) revealed that the complexes remain almost stable up to 230-260 °C. Beyond this range the complexes decomposed rapidly leaving a stable residue (metal oxide) in the case of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes. The Cu^{II} complexes did not form any stable residue and the decompo-

sition continued beyond 620 °C. Thermogram of FBPT complexes revealed their stability up to 220–290 °C. Beyond this range they showed rapid decomposition, denoting loss of ligand moiety. However they do not adhere to constant weight due to decomposition even up to ~ 620 °C.

Fig. 2

The electronic and magnetic data (Table 2) indicate Co^{II} complexes to be six-coordinated having an orbital singlet ground state with distorted octahedral environment (approx. C_2). The Cu^{II} complex are also distorted octahedral as evidenced from the occurrence of either two bands or a broad band envelope (Table 3). However, the magnetic and the electronic spectral aspects (Table 4) reflect a combination of special feature of Ni^{II} ions co-existing together in diamagnetic and paramagnetic tetragonal ligand field.

Based on foregoing observation and considering the *trans*-arrangement of the ligand in the complexes which is more stable than *cis*-arrangement because of less steric strain, the following tentative structure (Fig. 3) has been proposed for the complexes.

Fig. 3

Experimental

All the reagents used were of A.R. grade. The starting material 2-hydrazino-4-(phenylthiazole) and 2-hydrazino-4-(*p*-bromophenylthiazole) were prepared by refluxing ethanolic solution of phenacyl bromide and *p*-bromophenacyl bromide respectively with thiosemicarbazide. The hydrazones were obtained as coloured solids by refluxing above hydrazine compounds with furfural in the 1 : 1 molar ratio in the presence of few drops of piperidine.

The complexes were prepared by refluxing the ligands FPT and FBPT (0.004 mol) with the corresponding hydrated metal(II) salt (0.002 mol) in ethanolic medium for 2–3 h (for Cu^{II} complex 2 h and 3 h for other complexes) on a water bath with constant stirring. The complexes were filtered and allowed to cool during which coloured crystals separated out. The precipitates were dried *in vacuo* over fused CaCl_2 .

The complexes were analysed for their metal and halide contents by standard methods. Sulphur was estimated

Table 2. Electronic and magnetic moment values of the complexes : $[\text{Co}(\text{FPT}/\text{FBPT})_2\text{X}_2]$

Complexes	Ligand band position in cm^{-1} (nm)			ν_2 Calcd. (cm^{-1})	μ_{eff} (B.M.) at room temp.
	${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1) (cm^{-1})	${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ (ν_2) (cm^{-1})	${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(P)$ (ν_3) (cm^{-1})		
$[\text{Co}(\text{FPT})_2\text{Cl}_2]$	8700	19050	19700	19331	4.47
$[\text{Co}(\text{FPT})_2\text{Br}_2]$	8720	19010	19650	19402	4.68
$[\text{Co}(\text{FPT})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$	8900	19000	19620	18978	4.64
$[\text{Co}(\text{FBPT})_2\text{Cl}_2]$	9010	-	19965	19194	4.48
$[\text{Co}(\text{FBPT})_2\text{Br}_2]$	9546	-	20340	20315	4.42
$[\text{Co}(\text{FBPT})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$	9540	-	19836	20321	4.46

Table 3. Electronic and magnetic moment values of the complexes : [Cu(FPT/FBPT)₂X₂]

Complexes	Ligand band position in cm ⁻¹ (nm)				μ_{eff} (B.M.) at room temp.
	${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{2g}$ (cm ⁻¹)	${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3E_{2g}$ (cm ⁻¹)	${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ (cm ⁻¹)	${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ (cm ⁻¹)	
[Cu(FPT) ₂ Cl ₂]	-	-	-	15000-15600	1.86
[Cu(FPT) ₂ Br ₂]	-	13800	14800	-	1.88
[Cu(FPT) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]	-	13600	16500	-	1.91
[Cu(FBPT) ₂ Cl ₂]	-	-	-	13900-14500	1.80
[Cu(FBPT) ₂ Br ₂]	-	14285	16670	-	1.78
[Cu(FBPT) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]	-	14080	16390	-	1.82

Table 4. Electronic and magnetic moment values of the complexes : [Ni(FPT/FBPT)₂X₂]

Complexes	Ligand band position in cm ⁻¹ (nm)				μ_{eff} (B.M.) at room temp.
	${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3A_{2g}$ (cm ⁻¹)	${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3E_{2g}$ (cm ⁻¹)	${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}$ (cm ⁻¹)	${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$ (P) (cm ⁻¹)	
[Ni(FPT) ₂ Cl ₂]	133000	16400	20000	264000	2.26
[Ni(FPT) ₂ Br ₂]	13200	16300	20680	25980	2.14
[Ni(FPT) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]	13500	16500	20530	26120	2.18
[Ni(FBPT) ₂ Cl ₂]	13600	-	21000	26300	2.28
[Ni(FBPT) ₂ Br ₂]	13400	-	20800	25640	2.34
[Ni(FBPT) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]	13650	-	20200	25600	2.36

by as BaSO₄ where as nitrogen was determined by semi-micro combustion method. The compounds were analysed for their C, H, N contents following semimicro combustion method by MLW micro elementary CHN analyzer, halides were estimated by using Vohlard's method³. Magnetic susceptibility measurement were done by Gouy method at room temperature. Infrared spectra of the ligand and the complexes were recorded in KBr on a Perkin-Elmer 398 spectrophotometer. The conductance measurements were carried out with a Toshniwal conductivity bridge (model CL01-06) using 1×10^{-3} M DMF solution of the complexes. Thermogravimetric analyses were done with a Netzsch-429 automatic thermo analyzer by heating the complexes at the rate of 10 °C min⁻¹ taking 50 mg of sample in each case. The colour, analytical data, magnetic moment and molar conductance of the complexes are summarized in Table 1.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to UGC, New Delhi, for

financial support under M.R.P.

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